

The present work describes the study of saponin from the wood of this plant.

The crushed defatted wood was extracted with ethanol. The ethanol extract on concentration and usual treatment with different solvents and precipitation in acetone⁶ yielded a light brown substance which gave all the tests for saponin. On TLC in chloroform : methanol : water (65 : 45 : 10) it showed two major spots with traces of impurities. It was therefore purified by chromatography on a column of silica gel using chloroform : methanol : water as eluants and thus a colourless product m.p. 176°-78° was obtained which gave all the tests for saponin and has been named as Lebbekanin E. Besides this sucrose was also isolated and identified.

Lebbekanin E on acid hydrolysis gave acacic acid (27%; 3 β , 16 β , 21 β , trihydroxy-olean-12-ene-18 α H, 28-oic acid)⁷⁻⁹. The hydrolysate after neutralisation and deionisation showed the presence of four sugars identified as glucose, arabinose, xylose, and rhamnose by paper chromatography and TLC.

The sugars after separation by preparative paper chromatography were estimated by colorimetric method using phenol-sulphuric acid¹⁰ and the molar ratio of the sugars, glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose was found to be 4 : 2 : 1 : 1.

Lebbekanin E was unaffected on refluxing with 5% methanolic sodium hydroxide for 4 hr on a water bath and indicated that there is no ester linkage in Lebbekanin E and so the COOH group at C-28 is free.

Lebbekanin E on acetylation gave an acetate. The I.R. spectra of the acetate showed a γ -lactone band at 1770 cm⁻¹ which is absent in the I.R. spectrum of the saponin. This showed that during the acetylation process the 21-OH group and 28-COOH group have lactonised to form a γ -lactone as in case of acacic acid acetylation⁷⁻⁹. This clearly indicated that the 21-OH group and 28-COOH group are free and there is no sugar attachment on these positions. Therefore all the sugar molecules are attached to C-3 OH group and/or C-16 OH group.

On the basis of the data presented above partial structure (I) has been proposed for Lebbekanin E.

Fig. 1. R' and/or R'' = Glucose : Arabinose : Xylose : Rhamnose (4 : 2 : 1 : 1).

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Solid State Interaction between Urea oxalate and Phosphate of Iron and Aluminium

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ACID soils invariably contain iron and aluminium phosphates of low solubility¹. To increase the solubility so as to make these phosphates available to plants, is therefore of considerable interest in soil chemistry. In the present investigation the author attempts to find out the reaction of ferric and aluminium phosphates with urea oxalate on the lines recently reported by Kutty and Murthy² and Pant and Pathak³ in order to determine the conditions for making these phosphates of acid soils available to plants. The work consists of grinding a fixed amount of ferric or aluminium phosphate with varying amounts of urea oxalate so as to determine the particular ratio of the phosphate to urea oxalate necessary for rendering it completely water soluble.

Experimental

Since the exact nature of iron and aluminium phosphates in soils is as yet unknown, the experiments were carried out with laboratory reagent forms, FePO₄·2H₂O and AlPO₄·2H₂O. Urea oxalate was prepared from urea and oxalic acid⁴. It was purified by recrystallization. 1 g mole of ferric phosphate or aluminium phosphate was mixed with varying amounts of urea oxalate and ground in an agate mortar for 1-2 hr under dry conditions. To evaluate available phosphate 1 g of the mixture was leached with 250 ml of water, filtered and the amount of P₂O₅ obtained in the filtrate⁵ was taken as water soluble phosphate. The amount of P₂O₅ soluble in 100 ml of 2% citric acid solution in the residue after leaching with water was taken as the citrate soluble phosphate.

Results and Discussion

A solid state interaction occurs when varying amounts of urea oxalate and a fixed amount (1 g mole) of ferric or aluminium phosphate are ground together in the powdery form for 1 to 2 hr. The resulting product becomes completely water soluble when the mole ratio of the iron phosphate to urea oxalate is 1 : 1 because of the formation of soluble monoferric phosphate and ferric oxalate. In the case of aluminium system the resulting product becomes cent per cent water soluble only at the stage of 1 : 2 mole ratio, because of the conversion of sparingly soluble aluminium oxalate formed at the stage of 1 : 1 mole ratio into soluble complex oxalate compound. The complex formation is supported by the fact that at the stage of 1 : 2 mole ratio iron or aluminium could be not detected in the resulting product by ionizable reactions.

The nature of curves (Fig. 1) obtained on plotting the fraction of water soluble and citrate soluble P_2O_5 against varying amounts of ferric phosphate or aluminium phosphate and urea oxalate mixture clearly shows the experimental results.

Fig. 1.

It seems that the reaction between urea oxalate and iron or aluminium phosphate takes place due to the mobility of hydrogen and oxalate ions. At the points of contact of the two solids, protonation of the phosphate ions occurs as a result of the movement of labile H^+ ions from urea oxalate. Grinding increases the activation energy of the reaction and has a marked effect on the course of a solid state interaction. On grinding the textural and structural states of solids change and fresh surfaces of the reactants are exposed which enhances the rate of the

chemical reaction. To confirm that the reaction takes place in the solid state, physical methods like infra red spectrum and X-ray powder diffraction are adopted, where the solvent does not play any role at all. The work is being continued in this direction.

Thus it can be concluded that acid soils which invariably contain ferric and/or aluminium phosphate may be made available to plants in presence of excess of urea oxalate.

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Synthesis of analogues of Glycozolidine

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GLYCOZOLIDINE¹, $C_{15}H_{15}NO_2$, m.p. $161^{\circ}-62^{\circ}$, the second carbazole alkaloid isolated from the root bark of *Glycosmis pentaphylla* (Retz.) D.C., was shown to be a 3-methyl carbazole derivative with two methoxyl groups. One of the methoxyls was at 2 or 7 position. In consideration of the N.M.R. data of the compound 5 : 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl carbazole formulation (I) of glycozolidine was considered consistent². Recently it has been shown that some of the carbazole alkaloids or its congeners had antibiotic activity. In order to confirm the structure of glycozolidine and to test the antibiotic action of the carbazole derivatives, synthesis of 6 : 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl (II) and 5 : 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl (I) carbazole was undertaken. The present communication reports synthesis of these compounds, which were different from glycozolidine. Recently the structure of glycozolidine has been settled as 2 : 6-dimethoxy-3-methyl carbazole(III) ^{3a, 3b, 3c, 4}.

In the synthesis of these two carbazoles, we followed the method and procedure previously adopted in our laboratory⁶. The appropriate dimethoxy aniline derivative (V) were reacted with 2-hydroxymethylene-5-methyl cyclohexanone (IV) to yield the corresponding substituted hydrazones (VI). The hydrazones on indolisation with glacial acetic acid and hydrochloric acid furnished the appropriate 3-methyl-1-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole (VII). On reduction of the oxo compound by Wolff-Kishner method